

Comparison of urban layouts

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ABSTRACT

The present study provides a comprehensive analysis and comparison of the transportation networks in three of the world's most populous and dynamic cities: New York City, Tokyo, and Paris. Each city's transportation system reflects its unique historical, cultural, and socio-economic contexts, influencing urban mobility and accessibility. The research employs a multi-faceted approach, examining key components such as airports, railways, and subway systems. Quantitative metrics, including ridership statistics, coverage area, and operational efficiency, are utilized to evaluate each network's performance. Moreover, qualitative assessments highlight user experiences, accessibility challenges, and the impact of urban policies on transportation equity. The findings reveal significant strengths and weaknesses within each city's transportation framework, offering insights into best practices and potential areas for improvement. New York City's extensive subway system, characterised by its scale and 24-hour service, is contrasted with Tokyo's highly efficient and punctual rail network, which includes a blend of local and high-speed trains. Paris, known for its iconic Métro and extensive bus services, is analysed for its focus on sustainability and pedestrian-friendly initiatives. This comparative analysis not only contributes to the academic discourse on urban transportation but also serves as a valuable resource for policymakers and urban planners aiming to enhance mobility in metropolitan areas worldwide.

Keywords:

Urban Planning, Financial Districts, Transport Networks, Public Transport and Urban Livability

1. INTRODUCTION

Urban design has undergone significant transformations throughout history, reflecting the evolving needs and technologies of human societies. Ancient cities like Rome, Athens, and Babylon were designed around principles of order, symmetry, and hierarchy to convey power and grandeur. Their axial planning inspired the grid system seen in many modern cities (Urban Design lab Educations Pvt. Ltd., 2023). During the mediaeval period, more emphasis was placed on religion and commerce (Fainstein, 2024) where churches and markets became the centre of many cities. Most European cities with narrow streets were built around the 5th and 6th century AD. During the Renaissance, cities began to focus on creating beautiful spaces around the concept of humanism, involving harmony and symmetry. Zoning, transportation, and green spaces became the norm after the Industrial Revolution.

Contemporary urban design focuses on functionality and sustainability. Cities had to become more accommodating to expanding transportation networks and increasing population. Understanding urban design is impossible without understanding urban planning principles. One of the most important models is the concentric zone model known as the *Burgess model*. Developed by sociologist Ernest Burgess in 1925, this model depicts cities spatially organized into a series of concentric rings emanating from the central business district (CBD).

Second model is the *multiple nuclei model* (Harris and Ullman, 1945) which challenges the idea of a single central business district and proposes that cities have multiple centres of economic and social activity. Thirdly, the *grid layout* is a fundamental theory of urban planning that has been widely adopted across various cultures and historical periods (Katagiri et al., 2022b). It involves dividing a city into a series of rectangular blocks, with streets running at right angles to each other, forming a grid pattern. It offers economical land distribution, promotes pedestrian movement, and boasts easy navigation.

New York City, Tokyo, and Paris exhibit distinct urban planning philosophies shaped by their historical contexts and cultural values. New York City utilizes a grid layout established in the 1811 Commissioners' Plan, promoting efficient navigation and high-density development, particularly in Manhattan. In contrast, Tokyo evolved organically, characterized by a blend of traditional and modern elements. Its urban structure is influenced by the Yamanote Line, creating multiple centers of activity rather than a single central business district, reflecting its rapid post-war development and emphasis on transit-oriented growth. Paris, with its historical focus on aesthetics and humanism, features radial avenues and grand boulevards that prioritize beauty and social interaction. This design fosters a sense of order and hierarchy.

Together, these cities illustrate diverse strategies in urban planning that reflect their unique identities and functional needs.

Urban design has a significant impact on various aspects of urban environments and the people who inhabit them. Public transportation is arguably the most important feature of urban areas. Mass transportation hubs like railway terminals, bus terminals, and airports, are essential for the movement of people in and out. Pedestrian-friendly and bikeable cities can promote physical activity, reduce traffic congestion, and improve air quality. Effective waste management systems are important to send waste where it is treated properly rather than to landfills, forests, rivers, or oceans.

1.1 Aim of study

This study aims to evaluate the operational performance of the transportation networks in New York City, Tokyo, and Paris. Quantitative metrics (like ridership statistics and coverage area) and qualitative assessments (such as user experiences and accessibility challenges) are utilized to this end. The study seeks to identify strengths, weaknesses, and innovative practices in these urban transportation systems to inform improvements and offer insights for policymakers and urban planners worldwide.

The present study compares the urban layouts and features of three different cities: New York City, Singapore, Sydney, and Tokyo. Each uses different urban planning theories and has also been seen at the top of the lists of City Quality of Life indices frequently.

1.2 Airports

1. New York

The city is built around a grid layout of avenues running north to south and streets running east to west. Described by many as the greatest city on Earth, it has no shortage of impressive features.

New York City's airport system is a critical component of its urban planning, reflecting a complex interplay of transportation needs, economic development, and land use considerations. The city's airports, primarily John F. Kennedy International Airport (JFK), LaGuardia Airport (LGA), and Newark Liberty International Airport (EWR), serve as major hubs for both domestic and international travel, significantly influencing the metropolitan area's structure and economy (Forno, 2023).

Figure 1: *Location of NYC's three airports*

The placement of these airports is strategic, aimed at maximizing accessibility while minimizing disruption to urban life. JFK and LGA are located in Queens, while EWR is situated in New Jersey which allows for efficient service to different parts of the metropolitan area, catering to a diverse passenger base. The airports are integrated into the regional transportation network, with connections to mass transit systems like the AirTrain, which links JFK and EWR to the city's subway and rail networks.

LaGuardia was the first airport to open in the city in 1939. Construction on the \$20 million project began in 1937, with a landfill from Rikers Island being used to expand the site. The airport officially opened on December 2, 1939, as the New York Municipal Airport-LaGuardia Field. Its four runways at 45-degree angles to each other were an impressive feat of engineering for the time. After LaGuardia's opening in 1939, concerns quickly mounted about passenger congestion led to Planning for a larger airport near LaGuardia. The most notable aspect of the renovation is the complete overhaul of Terminal B, which was completed in 2023. This project will replace the old terminal with a modern facility featuring 35 gates across two concourses. The new terminal includes an expansive 850,000-square-foot Arrivals and Departures Hall, designed to enhance passenger flow and comfort(The \$8BN Plan to Save New York's Most Hated Airport, 2022.).

Fig 2A) LaGuardia's old Terminal
courtesy of LaGuardia Gateway Partners.

Fig 2B) The new Terminal B. Image

John F. Kennedy International Airport was made with six runways and five terminals to alleviate congestion and make new space for air travel. By the 1950s, JFK had become the world's busiest airport for international air traffic. The establishment of JFK significantly reduced the pressure on LaGuardia, allowing it to focus on domestic flights while JFK handled the international and long-haul traffic. It is undergoing a renovation that is a significant undertaking aimed at transforming its facilities and improving passenger experience.

John F. Kennedy Airport is also undergoing a major renovation. With more than 55M annual passengers today, it is among the busiest airports in the country. The huge upgrade plan features the upgrading of terminals and facilitating the roadway and the transit system that connect them. There will be two new terminals: Terminal One and Terminal Six. T1 will feature 23 gates and 2.5 million square feet. Terminal Six will take up 1.2 million square feet of space over a two-level concourse. A huge new check-in space will have a centralised security area, meaning travelers won't have to lug their bags everywhere. It also features a multi-level parking facility with about 2,000 spaces and an eco-friendly timbered exterior. A 122-metre pedestrian bridge equipped with rainwater harvesting technology will link it to New Terminal One.

2. Tokyo

The Haneda Airport is one of the international airports in the Greater Tokyo Area, located within city limits. Serving as the main headquarters of Japan's two biggest airlines, Japan Airlines, and All Nippon Airways, it allows the country to compete with international airlines (Ryall & Ryall, 2024). Its traffic was around 78.7 million in 2023 and is currently ranked as the fifth busiest airport worldwide (Number of International Flight Passengers at Japanese Airports Bounces Back in 2023, 2024).

Opened in 1931, Haneda Airport initially served as a base for domestic flights and was strategically located just 14 kilometres south of central Tokyo. The airport underwent several expansions and improvements throughout the 1930s and 1940s, adapting to the increasing

demand for air travel. After World War II, Haneda became the primary airport for international flights to and from Japan, particularly as the country began to rebuild and modernize (History of Haneda Airport | Enjoy Haneda Airport | Haneda Airport Passenger Terminal, 2020).

In the 1960s, a major urban planning initiative was undertaken to extend the airport's runways into Tokyo Bay allowing for larger aircraft and increased capacity. This project involved extensive land reclamation and infrastructure development, reshaping the city's coastline and integrating the airport with the surrounding urban fabric.

A striking feature of Haneda's development has been the significant use of land reclamation. In 1983, the Transport Ministry published a plan for expanding Haneda onto a new landfill in Tokyo Bay to increase capacity, reduce noise and make use of garbage generated by Tokyo. In July 1988, a new 3,000-metre (9,800 ft) runway opened on the landfill.

Fig 3A) Haneda airport in 1965

Fig 3B) Haneda airport in 1984

There are two sets of runways parallel to one another. Haneda airport has two runways parallel to each other pointing at 340 degrees. These parallel runways can be spaced to accommodate various weather conditions and wind directions, ensuring that operations can continue safely under different circumstances.

Narita Airport is the second international airport in the Greater Tokyo area. It is located 60 km east of Central Tokyo, forcing passengers to travel a long distance from the city to the airport. Construction of Narita Airport began in 1971, with the first terminal opening in 1978. The airport was designed to accommodate the growing international air traffic and was positioned as Japan's primary gateway to the world. Its construction involved extensive land reclamation and infrastructure development, which were significant challenges given the area's geography and existing land use.

The city of Tokyo saw a population size boom in the 1940's to 60's. It was increasingly difficult to find land large enough for an airport near to the city center. When the construction

started in 1971, the closest land the Japanese government could find for the airport near the city center was 60 kilometres away from it.

Fig. 4 Airport diagram of Tokyo Narita airport

Narita airport has strong cross-winds throughout the year-often more than 40 km/h. There are about 100 go-around cases every year and 90% of them occur because of low-level wind disturbances. This problem persists because of the poor urban planning of this airport. Wind at the airport hits at 20 and 330 degrees whereas both the runways of the airport are facing 270 degrees due to which alot of wind hits airplanes across their wings causing extreme arduous landings.

3. Paris

Charles de Gaulle (CDG) Airport, located about 25 km northeast of Paris, is the largest and busiest airport in France, and third busiest in Europe, handling over 67 million passengers annually. It serves as a major hub for international flights, offering connections to destinations worldwide. The airport features three main terminals, with extensive amenities including shops, restaurants, and lounges.

The airport was opened in 1974 and can be considered quite young as airports go. In 2016, Group ADP, formerly known as Aéroports de Paris, announced significant changes to the terminals of all Parisian airports-including CDG. The Satellite 1 terminals will be combined, including the terminals 2B and 2D. A new automated baggage sorting system and conveyor were installed under Terminal 2E Hall L to expedite the delivery time for the airlines operating the Paris-Charles de Gaulle hub. CDG Express, the direct express rail link from Paris to Charles de Gaulle Airport, is set to open in early 2027.

Fig 5: Airport diagram of Paris CDG

One commonly found problem in airports globally occurs at Paris CDG as well is crosswinds. Majority of the wind rose of CDG is pointed Southwest, whereas the runways of CDG are placed East to West(Paris Charles De Gaulle Airport Profile | CAPA, 2020).

Paris Orly Airport is the second principal airport of the city of Paris. Initially called Villeneuve-Orly Airport, the facility opened in the southern suburbs of Paris in 1932(60 Years of Paris-Orly Airport, 2021).This airport has a history of long use, having even been employed by the air force of Nazi Germany from 1940 to 1943 as they occupied France. Following the increased adoption of CDG, a development program in 2012 proposed to integrate the airport's two terminals with the construction of an 80,000-square-meter building to form one great terminal. On 14 April 2016, the Groupe ADP launched the Connect 2020 corporate strategy and the commercial brand Paris Aéroport was adopted by all Parisian airports including the Orly airport.

Fig 6. Airport diagram of Paris Orly

Crosswinds are less of a problem at Orly as the majority of the wind flows southwest, in alignment with the runway orientations(daryl herzmamm akrherz@iastate.edu, 2024). Group ADP recently launched a plan for the redevelopment of the Orly airport as a part of the 2035 development project.

The Paris-Orly development project is the precursor to the new airport development model led by Group ADP. It is part of the 2025 Pioneers roadmap to set out a new airport model in which airports become “hubs for mobility and clean energy solutions, and are propelled into the future through denser existing infrastructures”(Paucot-Landelle, 2024). However, it is also being made clear the project is not a development designed to accommodate more traffic.

Group ADP has outlined clear environmental goals for this airport, with an initial goal of zero net emissions on the ground from 2030. Other important environmental goals include:

- 30% of the surface area dedicated to biodiversity
- 6dB at the boundaries at night (10-11:30 p.m.)
- 40% reduction in electricity, heating and cooling consumption in the terminals by 2030
- 80% of non-hazardous waste recycled by 2030

Another major point of transportation accessibility is the new metro connection. The arrival of metro line 14, which will connect the airport to the centre of Paris in 25 minutes, will completely overhaul access to the airport, providing an opportunity to promote public transport and reduce car use as much as possible.

In 2023, CDG was voted the best European airport for the second year in a row and ranked 5th in the world's top 100 airports. One rather unique statistic that affects hundreds of passengers is the number of lost baggages. CDG had less than thirty misplaced baggages in the entirety of last year.

In conclusion, the airports of New York City, Tokyo, and Paris each reflect the unique characteristics and needs of their respective metropolitan areas, serving as vital hubs for international travel. John F. Kennedy International Airport (JFK) exemplifies New York's dynamic urban landscape, facilitating a high volume of domestic and international flights while continuously adapting to the evolving demands of air travel. Tokyo's Haneda Airport stands out for its proximity to the city center and efficient operations, making it a preferred choice for both domestic and international travelers, while also undergoing significant expansions to enhance passenger experience. Meanwhile, Charles de Gaulle Airport (CDG) in Paris, despite being relatively young, has rapidly established itself as a major European hub, with ongoing developments aimed at improving connectivity and sustainability. Together, these airports not only support their cities' economies but also embody the complexities of modern urban planning and transportation infrastructure, highlighting the critical role air travel plays in global connectivity.

1.3 Railways

1. New York

The city is home to two main railway stations, Penn Station and Grand Central Terminal. As of today, Penn Station is the busiest transportation facility in the Western Hemisphere, serving 600,000 passengers daily. Both of these are underground, running below the entire city (Penn Station, 2023). The evolution of railway terminals in New York City is closely tied to the growth of the railroads themselves.

Grand Central Terminal opened on February 2, 1913. Within 16 hours, an estimated 150,000 people had passed through the new station (Roberts, 2013). The terminal spurred development in the surrounding area, particularly in Terminal City, a commercial and office district created above where the tracks were covered. The terminal covers 48 acres (19 hectares) that has 44 platforms, the highest of any railroad station in the world (Grand Central Terminal, 2023). It technically holds the record officially as being the station with the highest number of platforms according to the Guinness World Record. The 30 tracks are split on two levels of the 44 underground platforms. The upper section was for inter-city trains, while the lower level provided means for commuter trains, so commuters and intercity passengers could board and alight without interfering with each other.

Penn Station was a creation of the Pennsylvania Railroad (PRR), established for direct rail access to New York City from the south (We Keep the Region Moving | Port Authority of New York and New Jersey, 2024). In 1968, Penn Central, forming from the merger of New York Central and Pennsylvania Railroads, leased Grand Central Terminal to UGP Properties, Inc., who proposed building a 55-story tower above the terminal. This plan would have demolished the main waiting room and part of the Main Concourse.

The idea behind this station was developed towards the end of the 19th century. It was developed to accommodate the increasing number of passengers going out from and entering Manhattan (NYC DOT - Infrastructure, 2024). Penn Station was then the biggest train station ever constructed occupying two city blocks between 7th and 8th Avenue and 31st and 33rd Street. It was an above-ground facility. It was one of the largest outdoor open spaces in New York City. The station stimulated development in the surrounding area known as Penn Plaza. It influenced the design of other grand train stations in the United States.

Construction started on a four-track double-decker tunnel connecting Queens and Manhattan in 1969. While the upper deck was eventually used for a subway line, the bottom deck was not finalized until 2022. The new route will shave up to 40 minutes from the time of traveling commuters along the route.

Fig 7. Penn Station in 1911

After World War II, declining rail travel and high maintenance costs led the Pennsylvania Railroad to sell the air rights above Penn Station in the 1950s for \$50 million (Smith J, 2023). This resulted in the controversial demolition of the original station between 1963-1966. The demolition of the Penn Station is considered a pivotal moment in the historic preservation movement, leading to the creation of stronger preservation laws and the New York City Landmarks Preservation Commission in 1965.

The current Penn Station was reconstructed between 1963 and 1968 as an underground facility beneath Madison Square Garden and Pennsylvania Plaza. The tracks and platforms remained from the original 1910 design but the concourses were changed to two for passengers and one for platforms.

Moynihan Train Hall opened in 2021 as an annex to Penn Station, primarily for Amtrak trains. It maintains the Beaux-Arts design style of the Farley Building, created by the same company that created the original Penn Station, McKim, Mead & White. The renovation project, which cost \$1.6 billion, restored original historic features and added a central atrium with a glass roof. The Moynihan Train Hall extends over 486,000 square feet and caters to 17 of the 21 Penn Station tracks on which Amtrak and LIRR services operate (The \$7BN Plan to Save New York's Most Hated Train Station, 2023).

Railway terminals are typically situated in central locations to maximise accessibility for commuters and travellers. Grand Central Terminal, located at 42nd Street and Park Avenue, serves as a vital nexus for the Metro-North Railroad, connecting the northern suburbs to Manhattan. This central placement facilitates easy transfers to other transportation modes, such as subways and buses, enhancing overall connectivity within the city.

The New York City Subway, inaugurated in 1904, has played a pivotal role in the city's growth. Its construction was part of a broader vision to create a comprehensive transit system that would facilitate the movement of people across the rapidly expanding urban environment. The subway allowed for the development of neighbourhoods far from Manhattan, enabling the city to grow outward rather than just upward, thus reshaping its demographic and economic patterns. The subway network enhances accessibility, connecting diverse neighbourhoods to job centres, schools, and essential services. The subway lines are all aligned vertically so that they almost correspond to an avenue. Most of them meet in the southern tip of the city, which is why that area is so crowded with subway stations.

2. Tokyo

Japan boasts one of the most advanced and extensive railway systems in the world, playing a crucial role in the country's transportation infrastructure. The railways are integral to daily life in Japan, facilitating efficient travel for millions of passengers and connecting urban centers with rural areas. All of Japan's railways are operated by Japan Railway Group (JR), a private company in business since 1987 (Central Japan Railway Company | Encyclopedia.com, n.d.).

The Japanese railway network is on a hub-and-spoke model. The capital city of Tokyo acts as the hub of the network where most lines either start in Tokyo and travel to smaller cities, or start in suburban areas and end in Tokyo (Britannica Money, 2022). In figure 8 the densest cluster of railway is in Tokyo, and smaller clusters can be seen around other major Japanese cities.

Fig 8. The three most populous Japanese cities

The biggest passenger railway company is Japan Railways East. It operates trains in all areas of the Greater Tokyo. The most notable train lines in Japan are the Shinkansen lines. The Shinkansen, commonly referred to as the bullet train, is Japan's high-speed rail network. It is recognized worldwide for its punctuality and advanced technology efficiency. The Shinkansen network has been in service since 1964, revolutionizing travel across the nation by connecting major cities and regions with spectacular speeds often at times above 300 km/h (186 mph)(Japan National Tourism Organization, 2022).

Japan was the first country to build dedicated railway lines for high-speed travel since most of the country was mountainous terrain; the existing network consisted of 1,067 mm narrow-gauge lines that made indirect routes and could not be adapted to higher speeds. For instance, assuming that the standard-gauge rail curve can take in a speed of 145 km/h (90 mph), the corresponding curve on narrow gauge rail will ensure a maximum allowable speed of 130 km/h (81 mph)(Shinkansen, 2024). In 1958, approval was granted by the government for the first Shinkansen lines connecting Tokyo and Osaka. The journey time between Tokyo and Osaka was shortened by the new line from 6h 40m to 4h and even to 3h 10m by the end of 1965. The first Shinkansen trains known as the 0 series moved at 210 km/h (130 mph) in their final configuration but was set at 220 km/h (137 mph).

The last of these trains, with their classic bullet-nosed appearance, have been retired on 30 November 2008(About the Shinkansen|Central Japan Railway Company, 2023).

Fig 10. A 0 series set in front of Mt. Fuji

After the initial success of the Shinkansen, multiple new lines were opened in the following decades. Presently, there are eight lines across the country. The *N700S Shinkansen* train makes the journey between Tokyo to Osaka in two and a half hours. Train stations in Greater Tokyo carry a combined 4 million passengers daily (Shinkansen: Bullet Trains in Japan, 2019). There are 11 stations that carry more than 200,000 people daily. The two largest and most notable stations; Shinjuku and Tokyo station, will be talked about in detail.

Shinjuku is a place with many desirable destinations, making it a major hub for commuters. The station serves as a connection point between multiple different transit lines, with about half of the 3 million daily users transferring from one line to another (East Japan Railway Company, 2012).

The second most important line in this station is the Odakyu line. The terminus for the Odakyu Line is parallel to the JR platforms on the west side. This is a major commuter route stretching southwest through the suburbs and out towards the coastal city of Odawara and the mountains of Hakone. The ten platforms are built on two levels beneath the Odakyu department store; three express service tracks (six platforms) on the ground level and two tracks (four platforms) on the level below. Each track has platforms on both sides in order to completely separate boarding and alighting passengers (Odakyu Railway: Connecting Shinjuku, Hakone and Enoshima, 2022).

In addition, the Keio Line concourse is situated west of the Odakyu Line concourse, two stories underground beneath the Keio department store. It comprises three platforms extending north to south (Keio Corporation Global Site, 2022). This suburban commuter line connects Shinjuku to the city of Hachiōji in the west. The two underground platforms of the Toei Ōedo Line extend from north to south and are located to the south of the Toei Shinjuku Line and Keio New Line facilities (Explore the Ōedo Line - JAPAN THIS!, 2020). It is on the 7th basement floor of Tokyo prefectural road 414 (Yotsuya-Tsunohazu Ave.).

All the purple paths are regular commutes through the station. The three-dimensional view of the station is like a maze of urban structure, but one thing highly appreciable about this is that it is highly efficient and clear in navigation due to the accessibility.

Tokyo Station is a vital transportation hub in Japan, renowned for its intricate infrastructure and extensive train lines. Serving an average of 380,000 passengers daily, it is a critical node in Tokyo's rail network, facilitating seamless connections between various train services (Tokyo Station City, 2016).

The station features a striking blend of historical architecture and modern facilities. The *Marunouchi Brick Station Building*, a designated Important Cultural Property, has been meticulously restored to preserve its original design while integrating contemporary amenities. This restoration is part of a broader initiative known as “Tokyo Station City,” which aims to enhance the urban environment surrounding the station, including improved traffic linkages and new commercial developments.

Three types of lines are present at Tokyo Station: JR East, JR Central, and Tokyo Metro. JR East operates six Shinkansen lines from Tokyo Station and eight regular-speed intercity lines. The only line JR Central operates is the Tokaido Shinkansen, the oldest and most used line. The Tokyo metro connects to the station via the Marunouchi Line.

Fig 11. Tokyo Station as seen from the sky in 2021

Japan plans to build a brand new Maglev Shinkansen line that would revolutionize rail travel. The project focuses primarily on the Chūō Shinkansen line, which will connect Tokyo, Nagoya, and Osaka, significantly reducing travel times between these key cities(Japan’s \$64BN Gamble on Levitating Bullet Trains Explained, 2021).

The Maglev (magnetic levitation) trains utilize superconducting magnets to eliminate the friction between wheels and track, which is the primary limiting factor for the speeds of modern trains. This technology allows trains to float above the tracks, enabling speeds of up to 500 km/h in testing. The Chūō Shinkansen is expected to cut travel time between Tokyo and Nagoya to about 40 minutes, compared to approximately 1 hour and 40 minutes on the current Tōkaidō Shinkansen. The first stage of the line is already under construction and is expected to finish in 2027. It will then be extended to Shin-Osaka station.

Fig 12. Map of the upcoming Chuo Shinkansen

3. Paris

Paris has five different major railway stations which serve more than 700 million people yearly(Soria-Lara & Banister, 2018). These stations are: Gare de Lyon, Gare du Nord, Gare de l'Est, Gare Montparnasse, Gare Saint Lazare, et Gare Saint Jacques.

The five railway stations are located strategically to maximise train traffic around the entirety of France. Paris is the centre of railways in France, even though it is located far from the geographical center. All TGV and LGV lines originate or conclude in one of Paris's railway stations. In fact, as the five stations are located in different corners of the city, the lines running from all stations flow to the corresponding part of the country.

Fig 13. Railway stations and the respective areas they serve on departure from Paris

The idea of the *TGV (Train de Grande Vitesse)* was first proposed in the 1960s. In 1976, the administration of the SNCF (the state-owned railway company of France) approved the first TGV line(Zeller, J., & Pruvost, 2017). The TGV 001 was the first prototype train built by SNCF in 1970. It was the first and only gas prototype TGV built, reaching speeds between 250-300 km/h. Two years later, this prototype broke the previous gas-turbine-powered locomotive speed record set in 1964 with a speed of 318 km/h,

After the oil crisis of 1973, it no longer seemed viable for the train of the future to be powered by a gas locomotive. The requirement was changed to fully electric operation, which resulted in an extensive redesign. The latest prototype was nicknamed “Zebulon”, and it ran over a million kilometres in testing over multiple years. The highest speed ever achieved by this was 309 km/h.

Efforts after this were focused on attaining the top speed which translated to TGV 100 coming from the aim speed of 100 metres per second(360 km/h). The TGV Sud-Est achieved a record of 380 km/h on 26 February 1981(TGVWeb - TGV Basics, 2017). Operation TGV 117 and TGV 140: Test programs were conducted by SNCF from November 1989 to May 1990, with the culmination of these tests resulting in a new world speed record at 515.3 km/h

(143.1 m/s or 320.3 mph) set on 18 May 1990. The most recent record, taken in 2007, was 574 km/h, achieved by TGV 150.

The first public run of the TGV was in 1981. It was 17 years after the first run of the Shinkansen, on the other hand, it ran at an initial speed of 300 km/h rather than 210. There has been development in the TGV from 1981 to the present(Zembri, 2011). Each model has been more efficient than the last; whether that be in terms of passenger capacity, power-to-weight ratio, or average speed.

1.4 Subways

1. New York

The New York City Subway is one of the world's oldest most-used public transit systems with 472 stations in operation. It is a critical component of the city's public transportation infrastructure and has a rich history that dates back to its inception in 1904("New York City Subway System Opens," 2019). Originally launched as the Interborough Rapid Transit (IRT) system, it has evolved into one of the largest and most complex subway networks in the world, currently encompassing 244 miles of track. Serving approximately 5.5 million riders daily, the subway is a symbol of the city's resilience and adaptability(ASCE Metropolitan Section - First New York City Subway, 2018).

The idea of an underground transit system in New York City started at the end of the 19th century, triggered by fast-growing population and urbanization that characterized the period following the Civil War. On February 21, 1900, the transport commission signed a contract with Rapid Transit Construction Company regarding the building of the subway and granted a 50-year operating lease from the opening of the line(New York City Transportation authority, 2023). The initial construction method was cut-and-cover. The street would be dug up to build the subway line before being rebuilt.

Fig 14. 1939 expansion plans

By the 1930s, the lines were owned by three companies: the Interborough Rapid Transit Company (IRT), the Brooklyn Rapid Transit Company (BRT), and the Independent Subway System (IND). In 1953, the New York City Transit Authority took over the subway and bus operations in the city. The 1970s and 80s were rough times for the NYC subway because of rampant delays, track problems, and graffiti. The great recovery of the 1990s brought graffiti-free cars, six stations, and 250 new trains (McDonald, J. 2018).

Fig 15. Map of the present subway system:

The rail in dark pink is 625V and is used by all lines of the New York City subway. The densest area on the map is Lower Manhattan as most bridges and tunnels to cross the East River are located there. Most lines in Manhattan follow certain avenues-wide roads parallel to each other that run up and down the island.

2. Tokyo

The Tokyo Subway is made of two different systems: The Tokyo Metro and the Toei Subway. Combined, they operate 304 km of track, 13 lines, and 286 stations, serving 3.93 billion people each year, and 6.84 million every single day (Hasegawa & Y., 2015).

The Tokyo subway is one of the oldest in the world, with its first line from Shimbashi to Yokohama opening in 1872. However, the Tokyo subway system officially began with the opening of the Ginza Line in 1927. The 1960s and 1970s saw rapid expansion with several lines. During this time, advancements like automatic train control systems were implemented to enhance safety and efficiency. The Tokyo Metro was formally established as a corporation in 2004, succeeding the Teito Rapid Transit Authority, which had operated the subway since 1941 (Boonekamp et al., 2018).

Tokyo was built as multiple smaller cities inside one huge city that would span a great land area. Therefore, the initial motive of the Tokyo Metro was to connect the smaller cities to the best of their capacity.

Fig 16. Different sub-cities within Tokyo seen from above

This was a huge success in the early decades of the Metro. This is exposed by the statistic that shows that there are only 0.54 cars per household in Tokyo(Kiba-Janiak & Cheba, 2019). The metro has also seen ease-of-use changes in recent years. Tokyo introduced a smart card system that was compatible with all transportation networks of all Japanese cities(Tran et al., 2016). Essentially, their smart card allowed people to travel anywhere in Japan with the card. The people of Tokyo consider connectivity with nearby sub-cities important as the Tokyo Metro connects to trains that reach suburban areas around Tokyo and smaller cities tens of kilometers from the city centre.

Fig 17. Map of the Tokyo subway

The ease of use of all thirteen of Tokyo metro’s lines is remarkable. Each line is assigned a color, capital letter, and each of its stations is numbered in order.

3. Paris

Paris’s subway system is covers 246 kilometres and has 350 stations. Opened on July 19, 1900, during the Exposition Universelle, it has grown to become one of the busiest metro systems in the world(Map of the Metro, RER, Bus and Tramway Lines | RATP, 2020). Renowned for its Art Nouveau entrances and uniform architectural style, the Métro facilitates daily commutes for millions—averaging around 4.1 million passengers each day and stands as an iconic symbol of Parisian culture and urban life(Mines, 2020). Its comprehensive network connects key landmarks and neighbourhoods, making it an indispensable part of the city's public transportation landscape.

The history of the Paris Métro began in the late 19th century, driven by the need to alleviate growing traffic congestion in the city. Designed by engineer Fulgence Bienvenüe, the project was officially initiated in April 1896, with construction awarded to the Compagnie de Chemin de Fer Métropolitain in July 1897 (Gallo & S., 2018). The first line, connecting Porte Maillot to Porte de Vincennes, opened on July 19, 1900. Over the following decades, the network expanded rapidly; by 1920, ten lines were operational. The system continued to grow throughout the 20th century, adapting to modern needs with automation and extensions (Wind & Hedman, 2017).

The Paris metro was built to serve the innermost circle of the city. Since the innermost circle has only a circumference of 35 km, there is not a huge area to be served. This has resulted in a very dense layout of subway stations. On average, stations are only 550 metres apart (Ueda, T. & Fujita, 2017). The black circle depicts the innermost circle of Paris, where the last walls of the city were built for defense.

Fig18. Railroads in Paris sorted by electrification

The future of the Paris metro is the project: The Grand Paris Express. It is a project consisting of new rapid transit lines that will connect the suburbs of the city. It will even consist of driverless trains that will achieve an average speed of 60 km/h (Vickerman, R., & Dufour, 2020).

2. DISCUSSION

This section consists of themes of *Sustainability* and *Population Increase* by analysing the layout of New York, Tokyo and Paris.

Sustainability

Sustainability has become a recurring theme of transportation networks of modern cities as these cities have implemented various initiatives to reduce environmental impact, improve efficiency, and promote public health.

- **Airports**

- **New York's** LaGuardia Airport and John F. Kennedy International Airport (JFK) is undergoing major redevelopment. Both airports are incorporating LEED-certified designs, featuring energy-efficient buildings, solar power, and water recycling systems. JFK's new Terminal One will also have electric ground service equipment to cut down on emissions from fuel-based airport vehicles.
- Narita International Airport and Haneda Airport in **Tokyo** have adopted several eco-friendly measures. Narita is increasing the use of renewable energy, such as solar power, and implementing energy-efficient lighting and HVAC systems. Haneda focuses on minimizing energy consumption through building design and has improved waste management and water recycling.
- Paris's Charles de Gaulle (CDG) and Orly Airport have introduced green initiatives to minimize their environmental impact. CDG focuses on reducing carbon emissions through energy-efficient designs, such as thermal insulation and renewable energy sources like solar power. Both airports are also expanding the use of electric ground transportation and have ambitious goals to reduce overall carbon emissions.
- **Railway Stations**
 - **New York:** Penn Station and Grand Central Terminal, two of the city's largest transportation hubs, are transitioning to more energy-efficient operations. The Moynihan Train Hall, part of Penn Station, integrates sustainable design with energy-efficient lighting and solar panels. This reduces the station's carbon footprint while providing a more comfortable environment for passengers.
 - **Tokyo's** railway hubs, such as Tokyo Station and Shinjuku Station, are among the busiest in the world, but they are also highly energy-efficient. Tokyo Station has undergone renovations to include solar panels and energy-saving LED lighting. Both stations emphasize the integration of public transport with green technologies to minimize emissions.
 - **Paris's** Gare du Nord and Gare de Lyon are iconic railway stations that have integrated sustainability into their operations. Gare du Nord has been retrofitted to include more energy-efficient systems and aims to become one of Europe's first low-carbon train stations. The station also features extensive bike parking and supports eco-friendly commuting options.
- **Subways**
 - The **New York City Subway** is working on electrification upgrades to improve energy efficiency and reduce environmental impact. Efforts like regenerative braking, which captures and reuses energy from braking trains, help minimize energy waste. The MTA has also introduced energy-efficient trains and is phasing out older, less efficient models.
 - The **Tokyo Metro** is a pioneer in energy efficiency, employing regenerative braking systems and energy-efficient lighting across its network. Subway stations are designed to optimize natural light and reduce energy consumption. Additionally, many subway stations now feature solar panels and water conservation technologies to further reduce their environmental impact.

- The **Paris Métro** is heavily focused on sustainability, with many stations modernized to include energy-saving features like LED lighting and solar panels. The Grand Paris Express expansion project aims to reduce traffic congestion by adding more efficient, electric-powered lines, further lowering the city's carbon emissions.

Population Increase

Population Increase is a recurring theme in the transportation systems of New York, Tokyo, and Paris, particularly in their airports, railway stations, and subways. As global cities and economic hubs, they face immense pressure to accommodate rising passenger numbers while maintaining efficient and sustainable transportation systems.

- **Airports**

- **New York's** airports, including John F. Kennedy International Airport (JFK), LaGuardia (LGA), and Newark Liberty International Airport (EWR), handle tens of millions of passengers each year. Increasing global air traffic, especially in business and tourism, has led to extensive airport expansions and modernization projects. JFK's redevelopment, which includes a \$13 billion overhaul, aims to expand capacity and improve facilities to handle future passenger growth. LaGuardia's recent transformation is also designed to meet rising demand, with new terminals and improved efficiency.
- **Tokyo's** Narita International Airport and Haneda Airport are among the busiest in Asia, handling millions of international and domestic passengers annually. As Japan continues to attract tourists and grows its role as a business hub, these airports are expanding to meet rising demand. Haneda, which is closer to the city center, has seen major renovations to increase capacity, including new international terminals and improved transport connections.
- **Paris's** Charles de Gaulle (CDG) and Orly Airport are key European gateways that face growing demand due to increased tourism, business travel, and their strategic importance as international hubs. CDG, in particular, handles over 76 million passengers annually and is expanding to meet future demand. The Terminal 4 project at CDG, which is expected to increase the airport's capacity by 35-40 million passengers per year, reflects the city's need to accommodate growing air traffic.

- **Railway Stations**

- **New York's** Penn Station and Grand Central Terminal are vital transportation hubs experiencing surging demand due to population growth and increased commuter traffic. Penn Station, which serves Amtrak, NJ Transit, and Long Island Rail Road, is undergoing significant redevelopment with the construction of the Moynihan Train Hall, aimed at easing congestion and improving passenger flow. The expansion is critical for meeting the growing volume of daily commuters traveling between New York and surrounding areas.
- **Tokyo** Station and Shinjuku Station are some of the busiest railway hubs in the world, with millions of passengers passing through daily. The high demand

for rail services, both for local commutes and long-distance travel, has led to continuous upgrades. Tokyo Station has expanded its Shinkansen (bullet train) platforms to handle more high-speed trains, addressing both domestic travel demand and the increase in tourism. Shinjuku Station, which serves more than 3.5 million passengers per day, has been modernized to improve passenger flow and reduce congestion.

- **Paris's** Gare du Nord and Gare de Lyon are crucial to the city's rail infrastructure, connecting local, national, and international routes. Gare du Nord, Europe's busiest train station, faces rising demand from commuters and international travelers using Eurostar and Thalys trains. Expansion plans are underway to double its capacity by 2024 to meet the needs of future passengers, including those traveling for the Paris Olympics. Similarly, Gare de Lyon, a major hub for high-speed TGV trains, is expanding to handle increasing numbers of travelers within France and across Europe.
- **Subways**
 - The **New York City** Subway system, one of the largest in the world, faces constant pressure to accommodate its 5 million daily riders. As ridership has grown, the system has had to address overcrowding, delays, and infrastructure strain. Efforts like the Second Avenue Subway expansion and upgrades to signaling systems are critical responses to rising demand and the need for greater capacity and reliability.
 - **Tokyo's** subway system, one of the most extensive and efficient globally, faces increasing demand due to the city's dense population and high reliance on public transport. Despite its efficiency, Tokyo Metro has had to expand services, improve train frequency, and upgrade its technology to handle the growing number of passengers. The Tsukuba Express Line and ongoing upgrades to the signaling systems are examples of efforts to accommodate more passengers and reduce overcrowding.
 - The **Paris Métro** experiences high demand due to the city's reliance on public transport, with millions of passengers daily. Rising population density and increasing tourist numbers are pushing the network to expand its capacity. The Grand Paris Express, the largest metro expansion in Europe, will add 200 km of new lines and 68 stations, dramatically increasing the system's capacity and addressing the rising population density

4. CONCLUSION

The study aimed to compare and contrast the urban transportation networks of three different cities, analysing their effectiveness, sustainability, and future-readiness. The paper aimed to identify innovative practices in each city's system, like Tokyo's punctuality, New York's extensive 24/7 operations, and Paris's sustainability efforts.

Penn Station and the Grand Central Terminal are adopting energy-efficient operations based

on sustainable design features, including energy-efficient lighting and solar panels. This is perhaps best exemplified in the Moynihan Train Hall at Penn Station, with its drastically reduced carbon footprints and passenger comfort. In Tokyo, railway stations such as Tokyo Station and Shinjuku Station, among others, have installed solar panels and LED lighting to reduce power consumption. In fact, the Tokyo Railway line is fully powered by renewable sources. Gare du Nord and Gare de Lyon have integrated sustainability into their practices, with Gare du Nord retrofitted to be energy efficient with the aim of becoming the first low-carbon train station in Europe. To encourage eco-friendly ways of reaching the station, it has a vast bike park.

MTA is modernizing the New York City Subway as part of efforts to electrify for efficiency in energy. New trains, energy-efficient, are being brought into the system, and old ones are being gradually replaced. The Tokyo Metro is at the forefront of energy efficiency by means of regenerative braking systems and optimized station designs to maximize natural light. Many stations also feature solar panels and water conservation technologies. Paris Métro nowadays has many modernized stations with energy-saving features inside the metro lines, incorporating LED lights and solar panels. It reduces traffic congestion due to electric-powered lines in the Grand Paris Express expansion project.

All three cities have some manifestation of technological changes in transport networks. For instance, smart technologies applied to managing traffic in Tokyo have greatly enhanced safety and decreased accidents on the roads. By employing the same technology, researchers postulate that there can be better operational efficiencies in other cities, coupled with safer systems of urban transportation.

The results highlight that continuous investments in transport infrastructure are of prime importance. Extensive metro systems or an upgraded road network—cases similar to Paris and Tokyo—are associated with beneficial impacts related to mobility efficiency and user satisfaction. The study implies that strategic investments in infrastructure are very important to maintain competitive and effective network-based urban transport.

While the research on comparison in transportation networks among New York City, Tokyo, and Paris gives insight into urban mobility and sustainability, there are a number of drawbacks that need to be factored in. First, information reliability is only as good as the data quality and availability. The findings may be skewed since the quality or completeness of data may vary from city to city, as each uses different methods when reporting statistics on transport.

The study also limits itself to a definite period and, therefore, may not catch the fluid characteristics of urban transportation. Changes in policy, infrastructure, or technology may pop up at any given time as easily as overnight perhaps before research is concluded to produce meaningful dataline. Furthermore, while the study lays much emphasis on energy efficiency and sustainability, it may gloss over other critical factors that affect transportation networks, such as social equity, user experience, and economic considerations. An all-inclusive analysis should therefore consider these dimensions to further present a more holistic image of urban transport dynamics.

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